

ROUND TABLE: THE CAATINGA, THE BEES AND THE POPULATIONS

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Abstract

The Caatinga, a unique biome in Brazil, is home to a diverse array of species, including key pollinators like bees, which play an essential role in maintaining both native ecosystems and agricultural productivity. Local communities rely heavily on these bees for pollinating crops, honey production, and other bee-related products. However, the increasing use of pesticides in agriculture is placing significant pressure on bee populations, threatening both biodiversity and the livelihoods of people who depend on these ecosystem services. Habitat contamination and the decline in pollinators may have far-reaching impacts on food security and ecological health. This round table brought together experts to discuss the BEESNESS Project, which includes collaborations between the Insecta Research

Group (UFRB), UNIOESTE, Universidade Positivo - Centro de Pesquisa da Universidade Positivo (Brazil), CIIMAR (Portugal), and Cardiff University (UK). The discussions focused on academic exchange, pesticide testing, and environmental profile in sampling sites in Pernambuco and Bahia, which present differing levels of anthropogenic impacts. Special attention was given to the effects of pesticide exposure on key native bee species, including *Tetragonisca angustula* (Jataí), *Nannotrigona testaceicornis* (Iraí), and *Melipona quadrifasciata anthidioides* (Mandaçaia). The session explored the challenges of ecotoxicological assessments using approaches ranging from enzymatic studies to multi-omics and ecosystem service consequences, integrating perspectives on ecosystem health and community livelihoods at risk. The findings highlight the critical need for data-driven environmental management strategies to conserve native bees and protect the broader ecological integrity of the Caatinga, ensuring the continued provision of pollination services to both natural and agricultural systems.

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